

GPM2220000811: ENSMUSP0000064155

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Sample information

Show ? (n) (w) Display as:

ENSMUSP0000064155: *Rif1*.p, no protein text annotation available
log(e) = -3035.3

(validate) (mrm)

1 MTAPGRSPLPLELLETWEDPSVPPGEQTDAYLTLTSRMTEGEEKVIAEIEKNSLSRLYTVL 60
61 KAHISSONSELSAALQALGFCLYNFRITSLSEANTCELLLTNGITKSSDKNVCTRAL 120
121 WVISKOTFPFAELVSKMVSIIIDSLVILSKGEIHSVAVDFEALNVIISHWFLHCRLEIOA 180
181 PVQMGEEESVFWAKLVIPLVVHSAQKHLRGGATALEMGMPLLLKQOEIALITEHLMTTKL 240
241 ISELOKLFKNKNETYVILKWLPLFKLLGKTLHRSGSFINSLLQLEELGFRSGTFMFKKIA 300
301 FIAWKSLIDNFALNPDIIISAKRLKLLMQLSSIHVFTETLALTKLEVWVYLLMRGQPQL 360
361 PANFEQVVCVPLIQSTISVDSIPSPQGNSSRGSASPGIPLTPGHKGCASPYGSPRGNLSSN 420
421 TGGMAAIPSIQLLGLMMLHLLGPEVLSFAKSHKIVLSLEPLEHPLISSPFFSKYAHT 480
481 LITAVHDSFVSQKGDASDAVVSATWKEKELISLVKSVTEAGNRKEKSGSEVLTLLIKSLENI 540
541 VKSEVFPVSKTTLVIMEITVKGPLPKVLGSPAYQVANMIDILNGTPALFLIQLIFNNNLLC 600
601 GVEDEKFFLNLETLVGCVLGSPPLAFSDSVLTVINQNAKQLVNHKEHLWRMWSMIVSPL 660
661 TDVIHQINEVNOGDALHNFSAIYGALTLPINHFSAQTFPTGTMKALIKTWSELYRAFT 720
721 RCASLVATAEENLCCLELSSKIMCSLEDEVSLDLLFLDRISHIIVMVDKIDFSPYNKKY 780
781 QPKIKSPQRSSDWSRKKKEPLGLKASLFLKLVKVIDTFHTLSLKETFSDTLLAIGNSIIS 840
841 MLSNVFGHISLPSMIREIFATFTRPLALLYENSKLDEAPKVYTSLNNKLEKLLGELVACL 900
901 QFSYLGAYDSELEHLSPLLCVIFLHKNKQIFKQSALLMNATFAKATALVYPEELKPIILR 960
961 QAKQRILLLLPGLNVEVMDDESSEFYSESTENSQNLVKSISGMERKSSGRDLSILAHTKDK 1020
1021 KKKVLSAKLLESSSPKIKSGKLLLEEKSTDFVFIPPEGKETKARVLTQHKEVLKTKR 1080
1081 CDIPALYNNLDASQDTLFAQFQSEESMESLTLTEKPKDAKIKKEQVESTIFIHQDAP 1140
1141 ENCGLDEHSENASLPCGGSVAETNPETLITGFDARKEVLISSKILSAESSSSTETS SVS 1200
1201 SSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRRTQFTILEKFDGSETRPFSPPLNNISSTVTVRNNQDNTTN 1260
1261 TDMPPKARKREVTKSKSDENLANAGKSSRRWSKAEQSVTKKSKPSTLSEQEEHSSENN 1320
1321 SPDLLSPTHEVSENDHDPSEATLEHKDGDPKPAVENASLEDLTHEEKVNGINMESKESTA 1380
1381 SVVARTFCIVNEDSOAALAPNPKTLRRSSRRRSEAVDSCSDSOERESGQKKERRKEEE 1440
1441 KIISKPLRKIDDKLPTOKLTDSEPIQENLTKGNTLPERTSGEPSVNAEIDQNRKPD 1500
1501 ENVSSEGGGGTLDNLDKSSSEKPLRGRTRYQTFRASQGLISAVENSESDSSEAKEEVSRKK 1560
1561 RSGKWKNRSSDSDIEEKEKKAEEVMTANQTLDCQAVPDVDVNAACQVCEKSTNNNR 1620
1621 VILQDSAGPADSIQAPPKGEKSKINKCVDSSFVSLVPESNLRNASKRLLYKQDNDS 1680
1681 NVRVSDSLSLSPKFTQVEQHKRRRRVRSKSCDCCGEKSQSQEKSFILGKNTESYAIKS 1740
1741 VEKTKTDLQVPEAPETREARDHAETKLAGPEPLVNFHVGLEBNCCTTGDSVKSEAELOE 1800
1801 ASLPPETVTVKERTYDASEAVSEIQGPCSENHSPAEDPGLSECKDISQKQLSENIGELD 1860
1861 ISDVGKACKVIAGSSPEGVETMELNVRNDAFVAADSEKSTQMDVSVDAVEEDNKKDECE 1920
1921 AVTTEVNVVEGVATEDFNQMDLSDTPIPVSKDVETEHAASGEIEGESNBSDSGSCCEMNK 1980
1981 EMGSHKAKOMSTEIDARVKEKTDILASAKSEALIGRLDVNTQSFVSDIEFMSSGERTVNC 2040
2041 KETSIEINKLDEAKLSCNEATVGNLDTLQEVGFTSEKVEKLPQCLLVQVASELGABSNTT 2100
2101 SPEKLELDSFGSVNESPSGMOQARCVWSPLASPSTSIKRGLEKRSQDEITSPVNRFRVS 2160
2161 FADPIYQAGLADDIDRRCSVVRSHSSNSPTIKSVKTSPTSHSKHNTTSAGFLSPGSQS 2220
2221 SKPKSPKCLITEMAQESMLSPTESVYPALVNCAASVDIILPQITSNMVARGLGQLIRAK 2280
2281 NIKTIGDLSTLTASEIKTLPFRSPKVFNVKALRVYHEQQMKSRLGLEEIPFDISEKAVN 2340
2341 GVESRVTSTDEEERFASDLLEPVLDTPLSKNLVAQISALALQLDSEDLYSYTGSLFEMH 2400
2401 EKLGTMANSIIRNLQSRNFWSPAHENS 2426

show legend ?

- Complete mods:** i. Carbamidomethyl@C, Label:+6 Da@K, Label:+6 Da@R
- Potential mods:** i. Oxidation@M, Phospho@S, Phospho@T, Phospho@Y
ii. Oxidation@M, Oxidation@W, Deamidated@N, Deamidated@Q
iii. Dioxidation@M, Dioxidation@W
- Protein-specific PTMs:** i. Phospho@S, Phospho@Y, Phospho@T, Acetyl@K
- N-terminal:** i. Ammonia-loss@Q, Ammonia-loss@C, Dehydrated@E (peptide)
ii. ragged, Acetyl (protein)

Identified Peptides

spectrum	log(e)	log(l)	m+h	delta	ζ	sequence	n
32490.1	-3.2	4.34	1428.6893	-0.0015	2/2	apgr ⁷ SPLELLETW ED ¹⁸ psvp	(46)
29518.1	-2.0	4.22	1444.6842	0.0009	2/2	apgr ⁷ SPLELLETW ED ¹⁸ psvp	(46)
29507.1	-1.8	4.25	1444.6842	-0.0019	2/2	apgr ⁷ SPLELLETW ED ¹⁸ psvp	(46)
32683.1	-1.1	4.21	1428.6893	0.0004	2/2	apgr ⁷ SPLELLETW ED ¹⁸ psvp	(46)
35429.1	-11.7	4.47	3347.6625	-0.0074	2/2	apgr ⁷ SPLELLETW EDPSVPPGEQTDAYLTLTSR ³⁶ mtge	(748)

model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
40225.1	-9.3	3.60	2346.3586	-0.0023	2/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
37716.1	-7.8	3.98	2347.3426	-0.0012	2/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
40227.1	-7.4	3.64	2346.3586	-0.0016	2/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
41096.1	-7.0	3.34	2347.3426	0.0014	2/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
40451.1	-7.0	3.45	2346.359	1.010	2/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
41075.1	-5.5	3.80	2347.3426	-0.0016	3/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
40220.1	-5.1	4.07	2346.3586	-0.0003	3/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
41188.1	-4.9	3.33	2347.343	1.001	2/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
41183.1	-4.0	3.40	2348.327	0.013	2/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
41082.1	-3.8	3.86	2347.3426	0.0019	3/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
41082.2	-3.8	3.86	2347.3426	0.0019	3/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
40217.1	-3.0	4.00	2346.3586	-0.0050	3/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
40494.1	-2.5	3.93	2346.3586	0.0043	3/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
41104.1	-2.3	3.92	2347.343	1.003	3/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
41104.2	-2.3	3.92	2347.343	1.003	3/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
41122.1	-2.1	4.02	2347.343	1.003	3/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
40531.1	-2.0	3.90	2346.359	1.006	3/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
37701.1	-1.7	4.20	2347.3426	0.0032	3/2	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	109 _{ssdk}							(2761)
39099.1	-6.5	3.43	2769.5647	0.0025	2/3	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	KSSDK 113 _{nvct}							(4)
39113.1	-5.9	3.48	2769.565	1.004	2/3	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	KSSDK 113 _{nvct}							(4)
39102.1	-5.0	3.44	2770.549	0.017	2/3	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	KSSDK 113 _{nvct}							(4)
39095.1	-3.1	3.42	2769.5647	0.0030	2/3	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	KSSDK 113 _{nvct}							(4)
39185.1	-3.1	4.12	2769.5647	-0.0002	3/3	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	KSSDK 113 _{nvct}							(4)
39180.1	-3.0	4.10	2769.5647	0.0007	3/3	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	KSSDK 113 _{nvct}							(4)
39037.1	-2.5	3.94	2769.5647	-0.0005	3/3	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	KSSDK 113 _{nvct}							(4)
39035.1	-2.3	3.94	2769.5647	0.0031	3/3	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	KSSDK 113 _{nvct}							(4)
39031.1	-1.7	3.85	2770.549	0.022	3/3	ynpr ⁸⁸	ITSGLSEANI QELLTLNGI	KSSDK 113 _{nvct}							(4)
25834.1	-2.6	3.96	2565.4356	-0.0050	3/4	ssdk ¹¹⁴	NVCTRALWVISKQTFFPAELVSK	135 _{mvss}							(6)
16276.1	-6.3	5.14	822.5179	-0.0007	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
16269.1	-5.5	4.99	822.5179	-0.0004	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
13846.1	-3.5	4.59	838.5128	-0.0005	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
13579.1	-3.3	4.81	838.5128	-0.0002	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
13831.1	-3.1	4.50	838.5128	0.0001	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
16474.1	-3.0	5.18	822.5179	-0.0004	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
14054.1	-2.9	4.50	838.5128	0.0000	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
10843.1	-2.9	4.64	854.5078	-0.0004	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
13795.1	-2.8	4.56	838.5128	-0.0003	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
16485.1	-2.7	5.01	822.5179	-0.0004	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
13588.1	-2.7	4.80	838.5128	-0.0006	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
14043.1	-2.3	4.52	838.5128	-0.0007	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
10823.1	-1.9	4.67	854.5078	-0.0009	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
11176.1	-1.9	4.89	854.5078	-0.0004	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
10837.1	-1.7	4.72	854.5078	-0.0002	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
14063.1	-1.5	4.45	838.5128	-0.0005	2/2	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISK 125 _{qtfp}								(2662)
25656.1	-9.8	4.03	1929.125	-0.013	2/3	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISKQTF PAELVSK	135 _{mvss}							(14)
25864.1	-8.5	3.97	1929.1247	-0.0043	2/3	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISKQTF PAELVSK	135 _{mvss}							(14)
25875.1	-8.5	3.91	1929.1247	0.0028	2/3	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISKQTF PAELVSK	135 _{mvss}							(14)
25665.1	-8.2	4.01	1929.1247	-0.0051	2/3	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISKQTF PAELVSK	135 _{mvss}							(14)
25886.1	-6.2	3.86	1929.1247	0.0009	2/3	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISKQTF PAELVSK	135 _{mvss}							(14)
25649.1	-4.4	4.40	1929.1247	-0.0004	3/3	vctr ¹¹⁹	ALWVISKQTF PAELVSK	135 _{mvss}							(14)

	model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
19058.1	-1.9	4.64	870.5179	-0.0009	2/2	mikk ²⁹⁹	IAFIAWKK	305slid								(1890)
19049.1	-1.8	4.64	870.5179	0.0004	2/2	mikk ²⁹⁹	IAFIAWKK	305slid								(1890)
19039.1	-1.8	4.64	870.5179	-0.0008	2/2	mikk ²⁹⁹	IAFIAWKK	305slid								(1890)
18781.1	-1.7	4.63	870.5179	-0.0002	2/2	mikk ²⁹⁹	IAFIAWKK	305slid								(1890)
38078.1	-1.8	3.68	2733.4723	0.0083	3/3	mikk ²⁹⁹	IAFIAWKS	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl					(18)
31463.1	-10.3	4.71	1896.9831	-0.0038	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
31475.1	-10.2	5.21	1896.9831	0.0013	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
31496.1	-6.8	4.72	1896.9831	-0.0006	3/3	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
31665.1	-6.7	4.53	1896.9831	0.0001	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
31676.1	-6.7	4.35	1896.9831	-0.0021	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
32205.1	-5.9	4.10	1897.9671	-0.0006	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
32180.1	-5.4	3.98	1897.9671	-0.0028	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
31487.1	-4.7	4.56	1896.9831	-0.0031	3/3	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
31494.1	-2.7	4.54	1896.9831	-0.0031	3/3	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
32196.1	-2.7	4.08	1897.9671	0.0044	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
31882.1	-2.5	3.81	1897.967	0.017	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
32791.1	-2.4	4.48	1897.967	0.996	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
32799.1	-2.4	4.45	1897.9671	-0.0028	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
32777.1	-1.0	4.53	1897.9671	-0.0082	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(20600)
28150.1	-6.7	4.06	2059.1043	0.0039	2/3	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAKR	323	kil						(745)
28130.1	-6.1	3.96	2059.1043	-0.0008	2/3	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAKR	323	kil						(745)
28162.1	-4.2	3.93	2059.1043	0.0009	2/3	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAKR	323	kil						(745)
28102.1	-3.5	4.55	2059.1043	-0.0015	3/3	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAKR	323	kil						(745)
28094.1	-2.6	4.59	2059.1043	-0.0006	3/3	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP	DILCSAKR	323	kil						(745)
16244.1	-2.7	4.33	1207.6447	0.0002	2/2	idnr ³¹²	ALNP	DILCSAK	322	rkl						(30)
17126.1	-1.8	4.93	1663.0126	-0.0013	3/4	sakr ³²⁴	LLKLLM	QPLSSIH	VR	337	tetl					(161)
18970.1	-7.9	4.49	1399.8185	0.0015	2/3	krlik ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH	VR	337	tetl						(13901)
15447.1	-6.9	4.78	1415.8135	-0.0014	2/3	krlik ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH	VR	337	tetl						(13901)
15437.1	-6.7	4.55	1415.8135	-0.0008	2/3	krlik ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH	VR	337	tetl						(13901)
18963.1	-6.3	4.52	1399.8185	-0.0038	2/3	krlik ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH	VR	337	tetl						(13901)
15415.1	-4.0	5.27	1415.8135	-0.0006	3/3	krlik ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH	VR	337	tetl						(13901)
15634.1	-3.3	5.55	1415.8135	-0.0010	3/3	krlik ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH	VR	337	tetl						(13901)
15425.1	-3.1	5.56	1415.8135	-0.0007	3/3	krlik ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH	VR	337	tetl						(13901)
15623.1	-2.8	5.68	1415.8135	-0.0006	3/3	krlik ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH	VR	337	tetl						(13901)
16656.1	-1.7	4.55	1416.7975	-0.0037	3/3	krlik ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH	VR	337	tetl						(13901)
7390.1	-3.4	4.78	882.5238	-0.0010	2/2	ihvr ³³⁸	TETLALTK	345	levw							(1757)
7397.1	-2.5	4.96	882.5238	-0.0006	2/2	ihvr ³³⁸	TETLALTK	345	levw							(1757)
33220.1	-4.9	4.66	1430.7596	0.0002	2/2	altr ³⁴⁶	LEVW	WYLLMR	355	lgpq						(192)
33421.1	-4.0	4.21	1430.7596	0.0036	2/2	altr ³⁴⁶	LEVW	WYLLMR	355	lgpq						(192)
33215.1	-3.9	4.64	1430.7596	-0.0001	2/2	altr ³⁴⁶	LEVW	WYLLMR	355	lgpq						(192)
38504.1	-6.6	4.09	3405.7359	0.0024	3/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE	QVCVPLIQST	ISVDSIPSPQ	GN	387	ssrg				(76)
38508.1	-5.9	4.03	3405.7359	-0.0002	3/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE	QVCVPLIQST	ISVDSIPSPQ	GN	387	ssrg				(76)
38436.1	-5.6	3.32	3405.7359	0.0086	2/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE	QVCVPLIQST	ISVDSIPSPQ	GN	387	ssrg				(76)
38357.1	-4.3	3.64	3405.7359	0.0009	3/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE	QVCVPLIQST	ISVDSIPSPQ	GN	387	ssrg				(76)
38335.1	-4.2	3.47	3405.736	2.002	3/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE	QVCVPLIQST	ISVDSIPSPQ	GN	387	ssrg				(76)
38418.1	-3.1	3.28	3405.736	1.003	2/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE	QVCVPLIQST	ISVDSIPSPQ	GN	387	ssrg				(76)
38350.1	-2.8	3.65	3405.7359	-0.0002	3/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE	QVCVPLIQST	ISVDSIPSPQ	GN	387	ssrg				(76)
35102.1	-10.6	5.79	3741.9212	0.0031	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE	QVCVPLIQST	ISVDSIPSPQ	GNSSR	390	gsas				(560)
34914.1	-9.6	4.27	3741.9212	0.0006	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE	QVCVPLIQST	ISVDSIPSPQ	GNSSR	390	gsas				(560)
35006.1	-8.7	3.90	3742.905	0.015	2/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE	QVCVPLIQST	ISVDSIPSPQ	GNSSR	390	gsas				(560)

	model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
35876.1	-1.8	3.80	3741.921	1.998	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVQVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas	(560)							
35876.2	-1.8	3.80	3742.905	1.013	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVQVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas	(560)							
36511.1	-1.7	3.43	3743.889	0.020	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVQVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas	(560)							
36511.2	-1.7	3.43	3743.889	0.020	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVQVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas	(560)							
37620.1	-1.6	3.62	3822.8715	-0.0088	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVQVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas	(560)							
37620.2	-1.6	3.62	3822.8715	-0.0088	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVQVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas	(560)							
35874.1	-1.6	3.75	3742.905	0.011	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVQVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas	(560)							
35874.2	-1.6	3.75	3742.905	0.011	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVQVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas	(560)							
35304.1	-1.6	3.69	3742.905	1.020	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVQVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas	(560)							
38473.1	-1.2	3.66	3822.8715	0.0015	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVQVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas	(560)							
18151.1	-2.9	3.98	1979.0135	0.0013	2/2	cvpl ³⁷²	IQSTISVDSI PSPQGNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas	(44)							
18130.1	-2.5	3.89	1979.014	0.017	2/2	cvpl ³⁷²	IQSTISVDSI PSPQGNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas	(44)							
9345.1	-8.0	4.40	1411.7635	0.0010	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
9353.1	-5.4	4.59	1411.7635	0.0007	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
12331.1	-4.7	4.70	1491.7299	0.0007	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
9552.1	-4.6	4.10	1411.7635	-0.0020	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
12310.1	-4.2	4.34	1491.7299	0.0043	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
9568.1	-3.7	3.95	1411.7635	-0.0037	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
12945.1	-3.6	4.37	1491.7299	-0.0022	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
12328.1	-2.9	5.04	1491.7299	-0.0009	3/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
12322.1	-2.6	4.53	1491.7299	0.0033	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
9561.1	-2.4	4.81	1411.7635	-0.0012	3/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
12339.1	-2.4	5.21	1491.7299	-0.0001	3/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
9549.1	-2.2	4.93	1411.7635	-0.0009	3/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
15834.1	-1.8	4.34	1571.6962	0.0014	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
12938.1	-1.6	4.27	1491.7299	0.0030	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
9351.1	-1.1	5.29	1411.7635	0.0000	3/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
12969.1	-1.1	4.99	1491.7299	-0.0005	3/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(3621)							
9421.1	-5.1	4.40	1267.7100	-0.0015	2/3	srgs ³⁹³	ASPGLSPLTP GHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(6)							
9409.1	-2.6	4.36	1267.7100	0.0007	2/3	srgs ³⁹³	ASPGLSPLTP GHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(6)							
9430.1	-2.0	4.38	1267.7100	0.0002	2/3	srgs ³⁹³	ASPGLSPLTP GHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(6)							
9418.1	-3.1	4.56	1109.6409	0.0004	2/3	gsas ³⁹⁵	PGLSPLTPGH K ⁴⁰⁵	gasp	(2)							
40686.1	-5.7	4.30	4011.0735	0.0001	3/3	gspr ⁴¹⁵	GNLSSNTGGM AAIPSIQLLG LEMMLHFLLG PEVLSFAK ⁴⁵²	qhki	(2)							
40617.1	-4.5	4.29	4013.042	2.030	3/3	gspr ⁴¹⁵	GNLSSNTGGM AAIPSIQLLG LEMMLHFLLG PEVLSFAK ⁴⁵²	qhki	(2)							
40621.1	-4.0	4.31	4013.042	2.039	3/3	gspr ⁴¹⁵	GNLSSNTGGM AAIPSIQLLG LEMMLHFLLG PEVLSFAK ⁴⁵²	qhki	(2)							
40621.2	-4.0	4.31	4013.042	2.039	3/3	gspr ⁴¹⁵	GNLSSNTGGM AAIPSIQLLG LEMMLHFLLG PEVLSFAK ⁴⁵²	qhki	(2)							
40772.1	-3.7	3.59	4012.058	1.019	3/3	gspr ⁴¹⁵	GNLSSNTGGM AAIPSIQLLG LEMMLHFLLG PEVLSFAK ⁴⁵²	qhki	(2)							
40749.1	-3.1	3.71	4011.074	0.997	3/3	gspr ⁴¹⁵	GNLSSNTGGM AAIPSIQLLG LEMMLHFLLG PEVLSFAK ⁴⁵²	qhki	(2)							
40756.1	-3.0	3.67	4012.058	0.020	3/3	gspr ⁴¹⁵	GNLSSNTGGM AAIPSIQLLG LEMMLHFLLG PEVLSFAK ⁴⁵²	qhki	(2)							
40543.1	-2.8	3.44	4012.058	0.018	3/3	gspr ⁴¹⁵	GNLSSNTGGM AAIPSIQLLG LEMMLHFLLG PEVLSFAK ⁴⁵²	qhki	(2)							
40562.1	-2.7	3.70	4011.074	0.012	3/3	gspr ⁴¹⁵	GNLSSNTGGM AAIPSIQLLG LEMMLHFLLG PEVLSFAK ⁴⁵²	qhki	(2)							
40762.1	-1.4	3.67	4012.058	1.025	3/3	gspr ⁴¹⁵	GNLSSNTGGM AAIPSIQLLG LEMMLHFLLG PEVLSFAK ⁴⁵²	qhki	(2)							
40554.1	-1.2	3.64	4012.058	1.009	3/3	gspr ⁴¹⁵	GNLSSNTGGM AAIPSIQLLG LEMMLHFLLG PEVLSFAK ⁴⁵²	qhki	(2)							
40540.1	-1.2	3.53	4013.042	0.039	3/3	gspr ⁴¹⁵	GNLSSNTGGM AAIPSIQLLG LEMMLHFLLG PEVLSFAK ⁴⁵²	qhki	(2)							
31788.1	-10.8	5.20	2346.3051	-0.0008	2/3	kqhk ⁴⁵⁶	IVLSLEPLEH PLISSPSFFS K ⁴⁷⁶	yaht	(1925)							
31777.1	-10.5	4.98	2346.3051	-0.0038	2/3	kqhk ⁴⁵⁶	IVLSLEPLEH PLISSPSFFS K ⁴⁷⁶	yaht	(1925)							
31985.1	-5.8	3.78	2346.3051	0.0001	2/3	kqhk ⁴⁵⁶	IVLSLEPLEH PLISSPSFFS K ⁴⁷⁶	yaht	(1925)							
32000.1	-5.4	3.69	2346.3051	-0.0016	2/3	kqhk ⁴⁵⁶	IVLSLEPLEH PLISSPSFFS K ⁴⁷⁶	yaht	(1925)							
31932.1	-2.8	5.21	2346.3051	-0.0006	3/3	kqhk ⁴⁵⁶	IVLSLEPLEH PLISSPSFFS K ⁴⁷⁶	yaht	(1925)							
31943.1	-2.4	5.03	2346.3051	0.0001	3/3	kqhk ⁴⁵⁶	IVLSLEPLEH PLISSPSFFS K ⁴⁷⁶	yaht	(1925)							

	model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
25938.1	-1.5	4.36	2170.0758	-0.0048	3/3	ksgk ¹⁰⁴⁴	LLEEEKSTDFVFIPPEGK	1061	etka							(1737)
25938.2	-1.5	4.36	2170.0758	-0.0048	3/3	ksgk ¹⁰⁴⁴	LLEEEKSTDFVFIPPEGK	1061	etka							(1737)
23029.1	-1.4	3.86	2090.1095	-0.0001	3/3	ksgk ¹⁰⁴⁴	LLEEEKSTDFVFIPPEGK	1061	etka							(1737)
25927.1	-1.1	4.42	2170.0758	-0.0012	3/3	ksgk ¹⁰⁴⁴	LLEEEKSTDFVFIPPEGK	1061	etka							(1737)
25927.2	-1.1	4.42	2170.0758	-0.0012	3/3	ksgk ¹⁰⁴⁴	LLEEEKSTDFVFIPPEGK	1061	etka							(1737)
21401.1	-7.1	5.87	1342.6985	-0.0002	2/2	eeek ¹⁰⁵⁰	STDFVFIPPE GK	1061	etka							(18148)
21619.1	-6.0	5.51	1342.6985	0.0002	2/2	eeek ¹⁰⁵⁰	STDFVFIPPE GK	1061	etka							(18148)
21608.1	-5.9	5.56	1342.6985	0.0008	2/2	eeek ¹⁰⁵⁰	STDFVFIPPE GK	1061	etka							(18148)
21391.1	-5.5	5.87	1342.6985	0.0002	2/2	eeek ¹⁰⁵⁰	STDFVFIPPE GK	1061	etka							(18148)
21833.1	-5.2	5.12	1342.6985	-0.0001	2/2	eeek ¹⁰⁵⁰	STDFVFIPPE GK	1061	etka							(18148)
22054.1	-5.1	4.79	1342.6985	-0.0004	2/2	eeek ¹⁰⁵⁰	STDFVFIPPE GK	1061	etka							(18148)
21822.1	-4.6	5.15	1342.6985	0.0001	2/2	eeek ¹⁰⁵⁰	STDFVFIPPE GK	1061	etka							(18148)
21184.1	-4.4	4.23	1342.6985	0.0003	2/2	eeek ¹⁰⁵⁰	STDFVFIPPE GK	1061	etka							(18148)
21194.1	-4.2	4.85	1342.6985	0.0002	2/2	eeek ¹⁰⁵⁰	STDFVFIPPE GK	1061	etka							(18148)
22066.1	-3.1	4.79	1342.6985	-0.0005	2/2	eeek ¹⁰⁵⁰	STDFVFIPPE GK	1061	etka							(18148)
32141.1	-6.5	3.55	4350.0355	-0.0014	3/3	ktkr ¹⁰⁸¹	DIPALYNNL DASQDTLFSAQFSQEESEMESLTLTEKPK	1118	edak							(20)
32115.1	-2.2	3.54	4350.0355	-0.0025	3/3	ktkr ¹⁰⁸¹	DIPALYNNL DASQDTLFSAQFSQEESEMESLTLTEKPK	1118	edak							(20)
15419.1	-5.0	4.19	1622.7003	-0.0083	2/2	kijk ¹¹²⁶	EEQMESTIFIHQD	1138	apen							(0)
15410.1	-3.2	4.11	1622.7003	-0.0004	2/2	kijk ¹¹²⁶	EEQMESTIFIHQD	1138	apen							(0)
26845.1	-6.2	3.70	4035.803	1.002	3/3	ihqd ¹¹³⁹	APENCGIDEH SENASLPNCGGSAVAETNPETLITGFDAE	1176	kevl							(0)
26893.1	-5.5	3.66	4035.803	1.017	3/3	ihqd ¹¹³⁹	APENCGIDEH SENASLPNCGGSAVAETNPETLITGFDAE	1176	kevl							(0)
26885.1	-4.6	3.69	4035.803	0.988	3/3	ihqd ¹¹³⁹	APENCGIDEH SENASLPNCGGSAVAETNPETLITGFDAE	1176	kevl							(0)
25800.1	-11.7	4.03	2100.9962	0.0068	2/2	slpn ¹¹⁵⁷	GGGSAVAETNPETLITGFDAE	1176	kevl							(50)
25791.1	-10.3	4.05	2100.9962	-0.0037	2/2	slpn ¹¹⁵⁷	GGGSAVAETNPETLITGFDAE	1176	kevl							(50)
31852.1	-10.0	3.80	2083.9696	-0.0008	2/2	slpn ¹¹⁵⁷	GGGSAVAETNPETLITGFDAE	1176	kevl							(50)
25809.1	-7.4	3.91	2100.9962	-0.0049	2/2	slpn ¹¹⁵⁷	GGGSAVAETNPETLITGFDAE	1176	kevl							(50)
31847.1	-7.1	3.78	2083.9696	-0.0045	2/2	slpn ¹¹⁵⁷	GGGSAVAETNPETLITGFDAE	1176	kevl							(50)
25813.1	-6.2	3.93	2100.9962	-0.0049	2/2	slpn ¹¹⁵⁷	GGGSAVAETNPETLITGFDAE	1176	kevl							(50)
25611.1	-5.1	3.99	1883.9441	-0.0019	2/2	pncg ¹¹⁵⁹	GSAVAETNPETLITGFDAE	1176	kevl							(10)
25377.1	-4.1	3.93	1826.9226	0.0005	2/2	ncgg ¹¹⁶⁰	SVAETNPETLITGFDAE	1176	kevl							(0)
18.1	-2.0	3.77	763.4656	-0.0001	2/2	dark ¹¹⁷⁸	VLISSK	1184	ilsa							(48)
13.1	-1.2	3.78	763.4656	-0.0007	2/2	dark ¹¹⁷⁸	VLISSK	1184	ilsa							(48)
102.1	-1.1	3.70	763.4656	-0.0010	2/2	dark ¹¹⁷⁸	VLISSK	1184	ilsa							(48)
21738.1	-8.4	4.09	3478.6763	-0.0032	2/2	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
21965.1	-8.1	5.03	3478.6763	0.0006	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
21972.1	-7.5	3.67	3478.6763	-0.0071	2/2	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
22619.1	-7.4	4.15	3478.6763	-0.0068	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
22724.1	-6.9	3.20	3479.6603	0.0070	2/2	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
22185.1	-6.6	4.52	3478.6763	-0.0016	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
22405.1	-5.7	4.32	3478.6763	-0.0068	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
22640.1	-5.6	4.04	3478.6763	-0.0016	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
22418.1	-5.2	4.18	3478.6763	-0.0071	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
22948.1	-5.0	4.05	3478.6763	-0.0002	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
22937.1	-4.9	4.04	3478.6763	-0.0042	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
24835.1	-4.8	3.68	3479.660	0.017	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
22304.1	-4.5	3.24	3479.660	0.010	2/2	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
21645.1	-4.4	4.09	3479.660	0.013	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
24554.1	-4.1	3.75	3478.676	1.000	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
23789.1	-3.9	3.96	3558.6426	-0.0021	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)
22637.1	-3.8	4.15	3478.6763	-0.0038	3/3	issk ¹¹⁸⁵	ILSAESSSSTETSVVSSSSVSNATFSGTTPQPTSRE	1219	rqtff							(662)

10603.1	-8.3	4.20	1309.6512	-0.0005	2/2	avpd ¹⁶⁰³	VDVNAAAVQVCEK	1614 ^{stnn}	(0)
10613.1	-6.8	4.22	1309.6512	-0.0000	2/2	avpd ¹⁶⁰³	VDVNAAAVQVCEK	1614 ^{stnn}	(0)
18049.1	-10.1	4.00	1812.9797	-0.0013	2/2	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
17597.1	-10.1	4.35	1812.9797	0.0041	2/2	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
17598.1	-8.1	4.41	1812.9797	0.0086	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
17813.1	-8.0	4.52	1812.9797	-0.0009	2/2	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
18025.1	-7.9	4.07	1812.9797	0.0023	2/2	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
17607.1	-7.2	4.40	1812.9797	0.0036	2/2	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
17824.1	-7.0	4.52	1812.9797	-0.0039	2/2	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
17816.1	-6.7	4.38	1812.9797	-0.0018	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
17615.1	-6.7	4.51	1812.9797	0.0005	2/2	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
17617.1	-6.3	4.40	1812.9797	0.0004	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
17827.1	-5.9	4.42	1812.9797	-0.0033	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
17838.1	-4.8	4.39	1812.9797	-0.0034	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
18043.1	-4.5	4.01	1812.9797	0.0003	2/2	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
18029.1	-2.1	4.41	1812.9797	-0.0020	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPK	1638 ^{geek}	(1235)
15055.1	-13.6	4.13	2262.2015	0.0002	2/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
15250.1	-13.3	4.59	2262.2015	-0.0005	2/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
15459.1	-11.8	4.39	2262.2015	-0.0010	2/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
15063.1	-11.2	4.26	2262.2015	0.0007	2/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
15470.1	-11.0	4.34	2262.2015	-0.0010	2/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
15719.1	-8.2	3.70	2262.2015	-0.0012	2/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
15667.1	-7.3	5.26	2262.2015	-0.0003	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
15645.1	-7.1	5.27	2262.2015	0.0005	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
15041.1	-7.1	4.08	2262.2015	-0.0037	2/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
15731.1	-6.3	3.82	2262.201	0.020	2/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
15865.1	-3.5	5.06	2262.2015	-0.0100	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
15948.1	-3.2	3.56	2263.1855	0.0033	2/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
16065.1	-3.0	4.55	2263.1855	0.0036	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
16155.1	-2.7	4.44	2262.2015	0.0012	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
14905.1	-2.7	4.00	2262.2015	0.0043	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
16292.1	-1.3	4.18	2263.1855	0.0072	3/3	nnnr ¹⁶²¹	VILQDSAGPA DSLQAPPKGEK	1642 ^{skin}	(2271)
25062.1	-9.0	5.23	1911.9576	-0.0020	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
32652.1	-8.3	4.44	1894.9311	0.0018	3/3	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
25073.1	-8.3	5.46	1911.9576	-0.0009	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
32660.1	-7.5	4.53	1894.9311	0.0021	3/3	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
32588.1	-7.4	4.87	1894.9311	-0.0013	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
25286.1	-5.4	4.16	1911.9576	0.0043	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
32578.1	-5.2	4.59	1894.9311	0.0005	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
25077.1	-3.7	4.75	1911.9576	0.0022	3/3	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
25084.1	-3.7	4.89	1911.9576	-0.0007	3/3	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
33108.1	-3.5	3.95	1894.9311	0.0026	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
33117.1	-3.5	3.93	1894.9311	-0.0041	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
25300.1	-3.4	4.10	1911.9576	0.0045	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
33603.1	-3.3	3.96	1895.9151	0.0079	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
33611.1	-3.1	4.01	1895.9151	0.0046	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
33594.1	-3.0	3.96	1895.9151	-0.0013	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
25272.1	-2.8	4.33	1911.9576	0.0007	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
26092.1	-2.5	3.98	1912.9416	-0.0002	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)
26082.1	-2.1	3.98	1912.9416	0.0012	2/2	kink ¹⁶⁴⁸	QVDSFVSLP VPESNLR	1664 ^{trna}	(3724)

	model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
22607.1	-6.0	5.18	3668.451	2.040	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
22574.1	-5.8	4.64	3666.4827	-0.0034	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
21063.1	-5.8	5.18	3586.5164	0.0005	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
22789.1	-5.7	4.01	3666.4827	-0.0012	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
24303.1	-5.6	4.27	3746.4490	-0.0006	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
22541.1	-5.2	3.81	3588.484	0.018	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
22978.1	-5.1	3.83	3667.4667	0.0003	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
21095.1	-5.1	5.61	3588.484	2.041	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
23965.1	-5.1	3.90	3667.4667	-0.0033	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
22995.1	-5.0	4.04	3667.4667	0.0069	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
23108.1	-4.9	3.91	3668.4507	-0.0074	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
21138.1	-4.7	5.94	3588.484	2.041	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
22987.1	-4.3	3.99	3667.467	0.014	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
21991.1	-4.2	3.93	3587.500	0.011	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
22775.1	-3.7	4.13	3666.4827	0.0025	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
23953.1	-3.4	3.79	3667.4667	-0.0041	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
22639.1	-3.4	5.45	3668.451	2.041	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
23620.1	-2.5	3.60	3668.451	0.016	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
24279.1	-1.8	4.10	3746.4490	-0.0079	3/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
21135.1	-1.4	3.20	3587.500	0.033	2/3	vkek ¹⁸¹⁴	TYDTDASEAV SEIQGPGSEN HSPAEDPGLS ECK	1846	disq				(1778)			
15664.1	-3.8	3.85	2991.304	0.013	3/3	ytdt ¹⁸¹⁹	ASEAVSEIQG PGENHSPAEDPGLSECK	1846	disq				(0)			
15697.1	-3.6	3.79	2991.3038	-0.0015	3/3	ytdt ¹⁸¹⁹	ASEAVSEIQG PGENHSPAEDPGLSECK	1846	disq				(0)			
22242.1	-4.5	4.37	2268.0681	-0.0032	3/3	seck ¹⁸⁴⁷	DISQQLSEN GELDISDVGK	1866	ackv				(0)			
22222.1	-3.9	4.41	2268.0681	0.0023	3/3	seck ¹⁸⁴⁷	DISQQLSEN GELDISDVGK	1866	ackv				(0)			
19199.1	-12.3	4.51	1610.7851	-0.0011	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
25216.1	-11.7	4.72	1592.7745	-0.0020	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
25925.1	-11.2	4.53	1593.7586	-0.0007	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
18989.1	-10.9	5.64	1610.7851	-0.0006	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
26117.1	-10.6	5.22	1593.7586	-0.0003	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
26405.1	-10.0	4.30	1593.7586	0.0022	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
25206.1	-9.8	4.48	1592.7745	-0.0057	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
18978.1	-9.7	5.64	1610.7851	-0.0004	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
26128.1	-9.6	5.26	1593.7586	-0.0001	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
19210.1	-8.5	4.61	1610.7851	-0.0013	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
26388.1	-8.4	4.35	1593.7586	-0.0019	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
25909.1	-8.3	4.41	1593.7586	0.0011	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
18002.1	-8.0	4.59	1609.8011	-0.0012	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
18198.1	-7.7	4.39	1609.8011	0.0002	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
18211.1	-7.6	4.32	1609.8011	0.0017	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
29599.1	-7.0	4.18	1672.7409	0.0015	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
25445.1	-7.0	4.40	1592.7745	-0.0031	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
17997.1	-5.2	4.43	1609.8011	-0.0000	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
18987.1	-4.9	4.43	1592.7745	-0.0058	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
22650.1	-4.7	4.18	1690.7514	-0.0008	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
18526.1	-3.8	3.96	1609.8011	0.0033	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
18547.1	-3.7	3.93	1609.8011	0.0018	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
21575.1	-3.7	3.52	1689.7674	0.0031	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
29591.1	-3.6	4.13	1672.7409	0.0026	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
19005.1	-3.5	4.45	1592.7745	0.0022	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			
30489.1	-3.5	4.00	1673.7249	-0.0005	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv				(4225)			

	model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
19014.1	-3.0	4.47	1592.7745	-0.0003	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv							(4225)
30494.1	-2.9	4.08	1673.7249	0.0009	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv							(4225)
18459.1	-2.6	4.05	1609.8011	-0.0025	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv							(4225)
22643.1	-2.6	4.23	1690.7514	-0.0005	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv							(4225)
30481.1	-2.2	4.00	1673.7249	0.0018	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv							(4225)
21564.1	-2.0	3.60	1689.7674	0.0025	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv							(4225)
21556.1	-1.7	3.61	1689.7674	0.0042	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv							(4225)
18609.1	-1.5	4.10	1609.801	2.017	2/2	isqk ¹⁸⁵²	QLSENGELDI SDVGK	1866	ackv							(4225)
17075.1	-13.7	5.08	1909.9631	-0.0008	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
17907.1	-11.8	4.07	1910.9471	-0.0027	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
20363.1	-11.4	4.88	1893.9682	0.0011	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
23742.1	-11.2	4.42	1973.9345	-0.0023	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
17068.1	-11.2	4.81	1909.9631	0.0009	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
17958.1	-11.0	4.28	1925.9580	-0.0006	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
23748.1	-11.0	4.48	1973.9345	-0.0003	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
17274.1	-10.8	4.40	1909.9631	0.0063	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
17967.1	-10.8	4.36	1925.9580	0.0013	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
17897.1	-10.7	4.12	1910.9471	0.0022	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
20371.1	-10.6	5.14	1893.9682	0.0006	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
23757.1	-10.3	4.63	1973.9345	-0.0010	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
20350.1	-9.8	4.50	1893.9682	0.0007	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
20381.1	-9.7	5.04	1893.9682	-0.0009	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
19969.1	-9.0	4.37	1989.9294	0.0019	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
17916.1	-8.9	4.09	1910.9471	0.0023	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
19997.1	-8.6	4.84	1989.9294	-0.0006	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
17288.1	-8.1	4.40	1909.9631	-0.0013	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
17298.1	-7.9	4.30	1909.9631	0.0005	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
23731.1	-7.7	4.43	1973.9345	0.0001	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
19975.1	-7.7	4.47	1989.9294	-0.0024	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
20018.1	-7.5	5.11	1989.9294	0.0002	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
20373.1	-7.4	4.93	1893.9682	0.0008	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
17086.1	-7.2	5.25	1909.9631	-0.0010	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
17077.1	-6.7	5.00	1909.9631	-0.0010	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
23737.1	-6.1	4.48	1973.9345	0.0001	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
20195.1	-6.0	3.90	1989.9294	0.0012	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
21279.1	-5.8	3.95	1894.9522	0.0049	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
20186.1	-4.2	4.10	1989.9294	0.0015	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
17256.1	-1.4	4.43	1910.947	2.019	2/2	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVR	1887	ndaf							(6668)
21548.1	-6.4	4.27	3064.4818	0.0078	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
21609.1	-6.2	5.21	3063.498	-0.014	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
21630.1	-5.9	5.24	3063.4978	-0.0023	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
21562.1	-5.9	4.47	3064.482	0.017	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
24286.1	-5.4	4.48	3048.4869	-0.0026	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
24055.1	-5.1	4.10	3144.4481	0.0009	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
22350.1	-4.9	4.29	3064.4818	0.0037	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
22350.2	-4.9	4.29	3064.4818	0.0037	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
24892.1	-4.0	3.94	3145.432	0.015	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
21683.1	-3.5	5.17	3065.466	2.037	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
24017.1	-3.1	4.07	3144.4481	-0.0098	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
25359.1	-2.9	4.67	3047.5029	0.0022	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)

	model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
22331.2	-2.5	4.25	3064.4818	0.0067	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
24885.1	-2.1	3.88	3145.432	0.016	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
21847.1	-2.1	4.11	3063.4978	0.0028	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
24046.1	-1.8	4.15	3144.4481	0.0023	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
24902.1	-1.7	3.88	3144.4481	0.0085	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
24302.1	-1.7	4.03	3143.4641	0.0081	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
22665.1	-1.6	3.96	3064.4818	0.0026	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
21666.1	-1.4	4.86	3065.466	2.036	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
25328.1	-1.4	4.47	3047.5029	0.0005	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
24249.1	-1.1	3.93	3143.4641	-0.0036	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
24277.1	-1.0	4.37	3048.4869	-0.0002	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
24369.1	-1.0	3.86	3144.448	0.018	3/3	kack ¹⁸⁷⁰	VIAGSSPEGV ETMELNVRND AFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(233)
7883.1	-8.7	4.35	1172.5525	0.0022	2/2	Invr ¹⁸⁸⁸	NDAFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(2339)
7873.1	-7.8	4.35	1172.5525	0.0004	2/2	Invr ¹⁸⁸⁸	NDAFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(2339)
7514.1	-7.7	6.12	1172.5525	0.0000	2/2	Invr ¹⁸⁸⁸	NDAFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(2339)
7525.1	-7.5	6.23	1172.5525	0.0004	2/2	Invr ¹⁸⁸⁸	NDAFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(2339)
7325.1	-6.6	4.14	1172.5525	0.0000	2/2	Invr ¹⁸⁸⁸	NDAFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(2339)
7304.1	-6.4	4.15	1172.5525	0.0011	2/2	Invr ¹⁸⁸⁸	NDAFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(2339)
7862.1	-6.0	4.37	1172.5525	0.0000	2/2	Invr ¹⁸⁸⁸	NDAFVAADSEK	1898	stqm							(2339)
12848.1	-15.0	4.46	1889.8376	0.0014	2/2	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNK	1915	kdec							(182)
12840.1	-13.6	4.34	1889.8376	-0.0007	2/2	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNK	1915	kdec							(182)
12832.1	-10.9	4.26	1889.8376	0.0008	2/2	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNK	1915	kdec							(182)
16328.1	-10.6	3.99	1873.8427	0.0020	2/2	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNK	1915	kdec							(182)
16336.1	-9.7	4.03	1873.8427	-0.0029	2/2	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNK	1915	kdec							(182)
12902.1	-4.4	4.70	1889.8376	-0.0012	3/2	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNK	1915	kdec							(182)
12878.1	-3.5	4.71	1889.8376	-0.0010	3/2	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNK	1915	kdec							(182)
13393.1	-11.8	4.11	2007.9578	-0.0003	2/3	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNKK	1916	dece							(344)
13408.1	-11.2	4.04	2007.9578	-0.0023	2/3	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNKK	1916	dece							(344)
13401.1	-11.0	4.03	2007.9578	0.0000	2/3	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNKK	1916	dece							(344)
10342.1	-11.0	4.09	2023.9527	-0.0003	2/3	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNKK	1916	dece							(344)
10327.1	-6.8	3.92	2023.9527	0.0016	2/3	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNKK	1916	dece							(344)
10334.1	-6.4	4.02	2023.9527	-0.0021	2/3	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNKK	1916	dece							(344)
13375.1	-5.4	4.67	2007.9578	0.0002	3/3	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNKK	1916	dece							(344)
10288.1	-5.3	4.51	2023.9527	-0.0019	3/3	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNKK	1916	dece							(344)
10298.1	-4.5	4.73	2023.9527	-0.0006	3/3	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNKK	1916	dece							(344)
13365.1	-3.9	4.60	2007.9578	0.0004	3/3	dsek ¹⁸⁹⁹	STQMDVSDV ATEEDNKK	1916	dece							(344)
27514.1	-11.6	3.70	3912.793	0.038	3/3	ednk ¹⁹¹⁶	KDEEAVTTE VNVEGVATED FNSGM DLSDT PIPVSK	1951	dvet							(26)
27533.1	-10.6	3.75	3912.793	0.019	3/3	ednk ¹⁹¹⁶	KDEEAVTTE VNVEGVATED FNSGM DLSDT PIPVSK	1951	dvet							(26)
27694.1	-10.3	3.65	3912.793	1.013	3/3	ednk ¹⁹¹⁶	KDEEAVTTE VNVEGVATED FNSGM DLSDT PIPVSK	1951	dvet							(26)
27740.1	-7.6	3.55	3913.777	0.038	3/3	ednk ¹⁹¹⁶	KDEEAVTTE VNVEGVATED FNSGM DLSDT PIPVSK	1951	dvet							(26)
27551.1	-7.5	3.85	3911.8088	-0.0091	3/3	ednk ¹⁹¹⁶	KDEEAVTTE VNVEGVATED FNSGM DLSDT PIPVSK	1951	dvet							(26)
27568.1	-7.1	3.83	3911.809	0.014	3/3	ednk ¹⁹¹⁶	KDEEAVTTE VNVEGVATED FNSGM DLSDT PIPVSK	1951	dvet							(26)
27760.1	-7.0	3.57	3912.7928	0.0041	3/3	ednk ¹⁹¹⁶	KDEEAVTTE VNVEGVATED FNSGM DLSDT PIPVSK	1951	dvet							(26)
27974.1	-6.0	3.44	3912.793	1.003	3/3	ednk ¹⁹¹⁶	KDEEAVTTE VNVEGVATED FNSGM DLSDT PIPVSK	1951	dvet							(26)
27819.1	-5.3	3.52	3912.793	0.018	3/3	ednk ¹⁹¹⁶	KDEEAVTTE VNVEGVATED FNSGM DLSDT PIPVSK	1951	dvet							(26)
28404.1	-3.4	3.46	3912.793	0.035	3/3	ednk ¹⁹¹⁶	KDEEAVTTE VNVEGVATED FNSGM DLSDT PIPVSK	1951	dvet							(26)
31008.1	-4.4	3.66	3778.678	0.023	3/3	dnkk ¹⁹¹⁷	DEEAVTTEV NVEGVATEDF NSGM DLSDT IPVSK	1951	dvet							(24)
31056.1	-3.4	3.67	3778.678	1.024	3/3	dnkk ¹⁹¹⁷	DEEAVTTEV NVEGVATEDF NSGM DLSDT IPVSK	1951	dvet							(24)
31209.1	-2.7	3.58	3778.678	0.020	3/3	dnkk ¹⁹¹⁷	DEEAVTTEV NVEGVATEDF NSGM DLSDT IPVSK	1951	dvet							(24)
31168.1	-2.1	3.56	3777.6937	0.0039	3/3	dnkk ¹⁹¹⁷	DEEAVTTEV NVEGVATEDF NSGM DLSDT IPVSK	1951	dvet							(24)

	model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
13856.1	-3.4	3.82	3133.2424	-0.0017	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
12942.1	-3.4	3.85	3149.2373	0.0046	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
16578.1	-3.3	3.79	3293.175	1.007	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
14894.1	-3.3	3.64	3310.154	0.019	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
14894.2	-3.3	3.64	3310.154	0.019	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
12904.1	-2.7	3.71	3149.2373	-0.0082	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
13868.1	-2.6	3.82	3133.2424	0.0042	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
13670.1	-2.5	3.75	3133.242	1.997	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
14926.1	-2.5	3.60	3309.1700	0.0098	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
15246.1	-2.4	3.68	3309.170	-0.014	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
13503.1	-2.0	3.72	3149.2373	0.0028	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
13977.1	-1.4	3.88	3134.2264	0.0082	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
11588.1	-1.0	3.67	3165.232	0.993	3/3	pvs ¹⁹⁵²	DVETEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC EEMNK	1980	emgs				(4657)			
8319.1	-7.0	4.67	1214.5777	-0.0005	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
8109.1	-6.1	4.32	1214.5777	-0.0017	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
8308.1	-5.3	4.85	1214.5777	-0.0005	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
8118.1	-5.0	4.58	1214.5777	-0.0001	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
3988.1	-3.3	4.11	1230.5726	0.0019	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
2685.1	-2.7	3.43	1246.5675	-0.0010	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
3994.1	-2.7	4.13	1230.5726	-0.0004	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
2541.1	-2.6	3.52	1246.5675	-0.0014	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
8126.1	-2.5	4.59	1214.5777	-0.0001	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
410.1	-1.6	3.39	1230.5726	-0.0016	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
7192.1	-1.5	4.02	1230.5726	-0.0074	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
2834.1	-1.3	3.56	1231.5566	-0.0026	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
2544.1	-1.3	3.50	1246.5675	-0.0023	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
422.1	-1.1	3.33	1230.5726	-0.0007	2/2	gshk ¹⁹⁸⁷	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vk	et			(3385)			
9935.1	-8.4	4.76	1273.7401	-0.0009	2/3	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SK	2009	seea				(1025)			
9948.1	-7.9	5.06	1273.7401	-0.0005	2/3	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SK	2009	seea				(1025)			
9957.1	-3.1	5.95	1273.7401	-0.0010	3/3	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SK	2009	seea				(1025)			
9946.1	-3.0	5.78	1273.7401	-0.0008	3/3	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SK	2009	seea				(1025)			
21669.1	-15.0	4.04	2135.2053	0.0033	2/4	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(86)			
21675.1	-15.0	3.95	2135.2053	0.0025	2/4	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(86)			
21623.1	-13.2	3.93	2135.2053	-0.0077	3/4	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(86)			
21686.1	-13.1	3.89	2135.2053	0.0082	2/4	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(86)			
21631.1	-9.2	4.09	2135.2053	-0.0044	3/4	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(86)			
21615.1	-5.1	3.93	2135.2053	-0.0097	3/4	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(86)			
9208.1	-4.4	5.56	1040.5566	-0.0005	2/2	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASK	2009	seea				(605)			
9198.1	-3.9	5.34	1040.5566	-0.0004	2/2	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASK	2009	seea				(605)			
9312.1	-3.1	4.65	1022.5460	-0.0005	2/2	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASK	2009	seea				(605)			
9408.1	-1.5	4.54	1040.5566	0.0009	2/2	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASK	2009	seea				(605)			
22791.1	-15.0	4.63	1902.0217	-0.0005	2/3	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(63)			
22800.1	-11.7	4.69	1902.0217	-0.0026	2/3	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(63)			
22870.1	-7.7	5.63	1902.0217	0.0004	3/3	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(63)			
36222.1	-5.8	3.58	4019.974	0.012	3/4	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(0)			
36205.1	-3.1	3.50	4019.974	0.018	3/4	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(0)			
36219.1	-1.9	3.60	4018.990	-0.011	3/4	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(0)			
36408.1	-1.3	3.46	4019.974	0.019	3/4	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(0)			
36408.2	-1.3	3.46	4019.974	0.019	3/4	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(0)			
7546.1	-2.2	6.24	880.4830	0.0003	2/2	sask ²⁰¹⁰	SEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(352)			

22668.1	-4.4	3.73	2406.1073	-0.0081	2/2	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EK	2077vekl	(827)
22150.1	-4.3	4.63	2406.1073	0.0002	3/2	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EK	2077vekl	(827)
21496.1	-4.2	4.95	2405.1232	0.0070	3/2	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EK	2077vekl	(827)
22614.1	-4.1	3.88	2406.1073	-0.0066	2/2	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EK	2077vekl	(827)
22154.1	-3.6	4.54	2406.1073	0.0008	3/2	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EK	2077vekl	(827)
22440.1	-3.6	4.17	2406.1073	-0.0014	3/2	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EK	2077vekl	(827)
21718.1	-3.3	4.07	2405.1232	0.0050	3/2	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EK	2077vekl	(827)
22431.1	-3.1	4.34	2406.1073	0.0002	3/2	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EK	2077vekl	(827)
23566.1	-2.8	3.55	2406.107	1.004	2/2	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EK	2077vekl	(827)
22651.1	-1.7	4.06	2406.1073	0.0002	3/2	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EK	2077vekl	(827)
20991.1	-9.6	4.12	2767.3493	-0.0014	2/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
20997.1	-7.4	4.28	2767.3493	0.0062	2/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
20963.1	-7.3	5.12	2767.3493	0.0016	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
23163.1	-4.5	4.33	2768.333	0.013	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
21084.1	-4.5	5.77	2767.3493	-0.0012	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
22164.1	-3.7	4.42	2768.3334	-0.0023	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
21106.1	-3.4	5.12	2767.3493	-0.0008	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
21632.1	-3.4	4.52	2768.3334	0.0070	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
23137.1	-3.3	4.14	2768.333	0.014	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
22893.1	-3.3	4.28	2768.3334	-0.0016	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
21627.1	-3.2	4.36	2768.333	0.024	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
21323.1	-2.5	3.95	2767.3493	0.0062	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
21981.1	-2.4	4.11	2768.3334	-0.0018	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
22159.1	-1.9	4.32	2768.3334	0.0043	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
22344.1	-1.6	3.79	2769.317	0.015	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
23149.1	-1.2	4.24	2768.3334	0.0076	3/3	deak ²⁰⁵⁶	LSGNEATVGN DTLQEVGFTS EKVEK	2080lpqc	(160)
31468.1	-10.1	4.21	2577.317	-0.013	2/2	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEK	2104ield	(1260)
31460.1	-7.1	4.10	2577.3172	-0.0007	2/2	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEK	2104ield	(1260)
31476.1	-6.6	4.17	2577.3172	-0.0027	2/2	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEK	2104ield	(1260)
34666.1	-6.2	4.03	2657.2835	0.0071	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEK	2104ield	(1260)
31464.1	-6.1	4.33	2577.3172	-0.0063	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEK	2104ield	(1260)
31453.1	-2.1	4.21	2577.3172	-0.0059	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEK	2104ield	(1260)
34611.1	-1.2	3.91	2657.284	1.020	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEK	2104ield	(1260)
34777.1	-12.2	4.48	4732.3119	0.0020	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
34866.1	-11.6	4.04	4734.280	2.052	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
35192.1	-11.1	3.58	4717.301	0.024	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
34937.1	-10.2	3.90	4734.280	2.035	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
36898.1	-10.1	3.78	4812.278	-0.011	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
34795.1	-9.6	4.41	4734.280	2.040	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
35368.1	-9.6	3.53	4717.301	0.029	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
34982.1	-9.4	3.82	4733.296	0.034	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
37107.1	-9.3	3.64	4797.267	0.018	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
35148.1	-8.7	3.53	4734.280	0.030	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
35362.1	-8.2	3.49	4734.280	1.017	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
34671.1	-8.0	4.30	4732.312	0.016	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
35184.1	-8.0	3.48	4717.301	0.022	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
35056.1	-7.8	3.69	4733.296	0.016	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
35615.1	-7.0	3.47	4733.296	0.022	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
36992.1	-6.9	3.31	4733.296	0.015	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)
35555.1	-6.8	3.57	4734.280	0.032	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124cvws	(58)

	model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
35070.1	-6.7	3.62	4733.2959	0.0098	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
36884.1	-6.6	3.82	4812.2782	0.0063	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
34728.1	-6.3	4.57	4732.3119	0.0009	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35389.1	-6.3	3.49	4717.301	1.011	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
36981.1	-5.7	3.79	4813.262	0.018	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35023.1	-5.4	3.74	4732.3119	-0.0046	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
36102.1	-5.3	3.23	4734.280	0.016	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
36645.1	-5.1	3.90	4814.246	2.047	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35176.1	-5.0	3.45	4716.317	2.016	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35763.1	-5.0	3.43	4733.296	1.024	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35736.1	-4.6	3.39	4733.296	1.029	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35266.1	-4.6	3.60	4733.296	0.027	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
36921.1	-4.5	3.83	4814.246	2.051	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
36921.2	-4.5	3.83	4814.246	2.051	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35316.1	-4.3	3.71	4716.3170	0.0052	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35301.1	-4.1	3.47	4734.280	0.021	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37302.1	-3.9	3.50	4813.2622	-0.0003	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37066.1	-3.8	3.75	4812.278	0.011	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37106.1	-3.8	3.67	4813.262	0.018	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37337.1	-3.7	3.27	4797.267	0.021	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37165.1	-3.6	3.58	4796.2833	0.0091	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35263.1	-3.6	3.58	4733.296	1.036	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35297.1	-3.5	3.55	4734.280	1.035	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35516.1	-3.4	3.52	4733.296	0.026	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
36652.1	-3.3	3.94	4812.2782	0.0063	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37056.1	-3.3	3.79	4812.2782	0.0008	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
36615.1	-3.3	3.61	4813.262	1.036	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37087.1	-3.2	3.53	4797.267	0.021	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37046.1	-3.1	3.25	4734.280	0.012	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35598.1	-2.9	3.54	4733.2959	-0.0049	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
34701.1	-2.7	4.33	4735.311	2.016	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
36030.1	-2.6	3.21	4733.296	1.018	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37217.1	-2.6	3.47	4814.246	2.025	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37217.2	-2.6	3.47	4814.246	2.025	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
34891.1	-2.6	3.94	4735.311	2.011	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37247.1	-2.4	3.41	4798.251	0.042	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35175.1	-2.1	3.51	4732.3119	-0.0071	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35260.1	-2.0	3.55	4732.312	1.001	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35402.1	-1.8	3.45	4717.301	0.024	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
35083.1	-1.8	3.59	4732.312	-0.010	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37256.1	-1.8	3.38	4798.251	0.047	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
36692.1	-1.4	4.01	4815.230	2.041	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37024.1	-1.3	3.27	4733.296	0.034	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37024.2	-1.3	3.27	4733.296	0.034	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
37712.1	-1.1	3.33	4813.262	0.014	3/3	kvek ²⁰⁸¹	LPOQLLVQVA SELGAESNTT SPEKLELDSF GSVNESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(58)			
19875.1	-13.9	4.49	2174.0126	0.0024	2/2	spek ²¹⁰⁵	LELDSFGSVN ESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(252)			
19869.1	-12.7	4.40	2174.0126	-0.0025	2/2	spek ²¹⁰⁵	LELDSFGSVN ESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(252)			
19860.1	-10.5	4.33	2174.0126	0.0012	2/2	spek ²¹⁰⁵	LELDSFGSVN ESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(252)			
19858.1	-10.4	4.47	2174.0126	0.0003	3/3	spek ²¹⁰⁵	LELDSFGSVN ESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(252)			
22160.1	-6.4	4.09	2158.0176	0.0019	3/3	spek ²¹⁰⁵	LELDSFGSVN ESPSGM QQAR	2124	cvws				(252)			

model		homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
8663.1	-7.3	4.37	1252.5999	-0.0008	2/2	glkr ²¹⁴⁵	SQEDEISPVN K	²¹⁵⁵ irrv					(3077)			
8655.1	-7.3	4.35	1252.5999	0.0004	2/2	glkr ²¹⁴⁵	SQEDEISPVN K	²¹⁵⁵ irrv					(3077)			
8644.1	-6.9	4.28	1252.5999	-0.0008	2/2	glkr ²¹⁴⁵	SQEDEISPVN K	²¹⁵⁵ irrv					(3077)			
7492.1	-5.5	4.39	1251.6159	0.0002	2/2	glkr ²¹⁴⁵	SQEDEISPVN K	²¹⁵⁵ irrv					(3077)			
7276.1	-5.3	4.67	1251.6159	-0.0001	2/2	glkr ²¹⁴⁵	SQEDEISPVN K	²¹⁵⁵ irrv					(3077)			
7286.1	-5.2	5.01	1251.6159	0.0004	2/2	glkr ²¹⁴⁵	SQEDEISPVN K	²¹⁵⁵ irrv					(3077)			
7481.1	-4.8	4.51	1251.6159	0.0006	2/2	glkr ²¹⁴⁵	SQEDEISPVN K	²¹⁵⁵ irrv					(3077)			
8777.1	-4.7	4.17	1331.5822	0.0010	2/2	glkr ²¹⁴⁵	SQEDEISPVN K	²¹⁵⁵ irrv					(3077)			
8785.1	-3.3	4.22	1331.5822	0.0003	2/2	glkr ²¹⁴⁵	SQEDEISPVN K	²¹⁵⁵ irrv					(3077)			
8792.1	-2.6	4.28	1331.5822	0.0003	2/2	glkr ²¹⁴⁵	SQEDEISPVN K	²¹⁵⁵ irrv					(3077)			
5688.1	-2.2	4.19	1251.6159	-0.0007	2/2	glkr ²¹⁴⁵	SQEDEISPVN K	²¹⁵⁵ irrv					(3077)			
8226.1	-1.5	4.15	1252.5999	-0.0033	2/2	glkr ²¹⁴⁵	SQEDEISPVN K	²¹⁵⁵ irrv					(3077)			
24014.1	-2.0	4.50	2134.0966	-0.0070	3/3	nkir ²¹⁵⁸	RVSFADPIYQ AGLADDIDR	²¹⁷⁶ rscsv					(1957)			
24063.1	-1.5	3.73	2134.097	0.994	2/3	nkir ²¹⁵⁸	RVSFADPIYQ AGLADDIDR	²¹⁷⁶ rscsv					(1957)			
21484.1	-7.0	4.66	2296.2179	-0.0008	3/4	nkir ²¹⁵⁸	RVSFADPIYQ AGLADDIDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(8296)			
21478.1	-5.1	4.49	2296.2179	-0.0008	3/4	nkir ²¹⁵⁸	RVSFADPIYQ AGLADDIDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(8296)			
21489.1	-4.9	4.93	2296.2179	-0.0010	3/4	nkir ²¹⁵⁸	RVSFADPIYQ AGLADDIDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(8296)			
22659.1	-4.2	4.16	2297.202	0.011	3/4	nkir ²¹⁵⁸	RVSFADPIYQ AGLADDIDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(8296)			
22625.1	-2.1	4.18	2297.2019	0.0079	3/4	nkir ²¹⁵⁸	RVSFADPIYQ AGLADDIDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(8296)			
21598.1	-1.9	5.59	2297.202	2.024	3/4	nkir ²¹⁵⁸	RVSFADPIYQ AGLADDIDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(8296)			
31957.1	-7.6	3.84	1809.8541	-0.0018	2/2	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDID	²¹⁷⁵ rscs					(0)			
31949.1	-3.4	3.84	1809.8541	-0.0024	2/2	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDID	²¹⁷⁵ rscs					(0)			
27690.1	-15.0	4.44	1971.9754	0.0003	2/2	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDIDR	²¹⁷⁶ rscsv					(8543)			
27716.1	-12.7	4.52	1971.9754	-0.0011	3/3	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDIDR	²¹⁷⁶ rscsv					(8543)			
27680.1	-11.4	4.29	1971.9754	-0.0077	2/2	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDIDR	²¹⁷⁶ rscsv					(8543)			
27705.1	-9.5	4.49	1971.9754	-0.0053	3/3	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDIDR	²¹⁷⁶ rscsv					(8543)			
27723.1	-7.9	4.59	1971.9754	-0.0016	3/3	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDIDR	²¹⁷⁶ rscsv					(8543)			
24729.1	-3.1	4.74	2134.0966	0.0020	3/3	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDIDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(12139)			
24833.1	-2.5	5.38	2135.081	2.024	2/3	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDIDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(12139)			
24758.1	-2.3	4.45	2134.0966	-0.0053	2/3	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDIDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(12139)			
24769.1	-2.2	4.80	2134.0966	-0.0001	2/3	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDIDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(12139)			
24952.1	-1.5	4.75	2134.0966	0.0020	3/3	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDIDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(12139)			
24930.1	-1.3	5.01	2134.0966	-0.0004	3/3	kirr ²¹⁵⁹	VSFADPIYQA GLADDIDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(12139)			
15568.1	-5.3	5.36	1614.8637	-0.0006	3/3	sfad ²¹⁶⁴	PIYQAGLADD IDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(765)			
15557.1	-3.6	5.14	1614.8637	-0.0011	3/3	sfad ²¹⁶⁴	PIYQAGLADD IDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(765)			
15592.1	-3.5	4.31	1614.8637	-0.0015	2/3	sfad ²¹⁶⁴	PIYQAGLADD IDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(765)			
21568.1	-3.2	3.91	1614.864	0.010	3/3	sfad ²¹⁶⁴	PIYQAGLADD IDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(765)			
15581.1	-2.0	4.22	1614.8637	-0.0006	2/3	sfad ²¹⁶⁴	PIYQAGLADD IDRR	²¹⁷⁷ csvv					(765)			
7758.1	-6.6	5.86	1100.5678	-0.0002	2/2	tsak ²²¹²	GFLSPGSQSS K	²²²² fksp					(887)			
7769.1	-6.0	5.74	1100.5678	-0.0001	2/2	tsak ²²¹²	GFLSPGSQSS K	²²²² fksp					(887)			
7557.1	-4.8	4.45	1100.5678	0.0005	2/2	tsak ²²¹²	GFLSPGSQSS K	²²²² fksp					(887)			
7567.1	-4.4	4.65	1100.5678	-0.0004	2/2	tsak ²²¹²	GFLSPGSQSS K	²²²² fksp					(887)			
7962.1	-1.2	4.28	1100.5678	0.0048	2/2	tsak ²²¹²	GFLSPGSQSS K	²²²² fksp					(887)			
39196.1	-4.8	3.35	4865.316	1.001	3/3	spkk ²²²⁹	CLITEMAQES MLSPTESVYP ALVNGAASVD IILPQITSNM WAR	²²⁷¹ glgq					(0)			
39196.2	-4.8	3.35	4865.316	1.001	3/3	spkk ²²²⁹	CLITEMAQES MLSPTESVYP ALVNGAASVD IILPQITSNM WAR	²²⁷¹ glgq					(0)			
39316.1	-2.5	3.20	4865.316	2.003	3/3	spkk ²²²⁹	CLITEMAQES MLSPTESVYP ALVNGAASVD IILPQITSNM WAR	²²⁷¹ glgq					(0)			
39316.2	-2.5	3.20	4865.316	2.003	3/3	spkk ²²²⁹	CLITEMAQES MLSPTESVYP ALVNGAASVD IILPQITSNM WAR	²²⁷¹ glgq					(0)			
43058.1	-1.7	3.06	4848.289	1.024	3/3	spkk ²²²⁹	CLITEMAQES MLSPTESVYP ALVNGAASVD IILPQITSNM WAR	²²⁷¹ glgq					(0)			
43058.2	-1.7	3.06	4848.289	1.024	3/3	spkk ²²²⁹	CLITEMAQES MLSPTESVYP ALVNGAASVD IILPQITSNM WAR	²²⁷¹ glgq					(0)			
39222.1	-1.7	3.38	4865.3158	0.0031	3/3	spkk ²²²⁹	CLITEMAQES MLSPTESVYP ALVNGAASVD IILPQITSNM WAR	²²⁷¹ glgq					(0)			

	model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
43119.1	-1.5	3.06	4847.3052	0.0048	3/3	spkk ²²²⁹	GLITEMAQESMLSPTESVYPALVNGAASVDIILPQITSNMWAR ²²⁷¹	glgq	(0)							
43119.2	-1.5	3.06	4847.3052	0.0048	3/3	spkk ²²²⁹	GLITEMAQESMLSPTESVYPALVNGAASVDIILPQITSNMWAR ²²⁷¹	glgq	(0)							
29023.1	-2.9	3.96	2008.0627	0.0027	2/2	lvnc ²²⁵⁴	AASVDIILPQITSNMWAR ²²⁷¹	glgq	(0)							
11987.1	-3.1	5.68	762.4928	-0.0002	2/2	mwar ²²⁷²	GLGQLR ²²⁷⁸	akni	(1207)							
11978.1	-1.1	5.38	762.4928	-0.0002	2/2	mwar ²²⁷²	GLGQLR ²²⁷⁸	akni	(1207)							
22108.1	-9.4	5.62	1454.8044	-0.0001	2/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22328.1	-8.8	5.47	1454.8044	0.0001	2/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22751.1	-7.2	4.34	1454.8044	0.0006	2/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22317.1	-7.2	5.53	1454.8044	0.0003	2/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22554.1	-6.3	4.56	1454.8044	0.0008	2/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22097.1	-6.2	5.28	1454.8044	0.0005	2/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22532.1	-5.8	4.69	1454.8044	0.0018	2/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22766.1	-5.0	4.33	1454.8044	0.0008	2/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22777.1	-4.5	4.33	1454.8044	0.0005	2/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22114.1	-4.0	4.88	1454.8044	-0.0020	3/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22329.1	-3.8	4.69	1454.8044	0.0014	3/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22339.1	-3.7	4.26	1454.8044	0.0009	3/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22120.1	-3.5	5.04	1454.8044	-0.0013	3/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
22972.1	-1.8	4.25	1454.8044	0.0011	2/2	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(36946)							
27304.1	-7.0	3.81	2041.1942	-0.0057	2/3	knik ²²⁸⁴	TIGDLSTLTA SEIK TLPISR ²³⁰²	spkv	(160)							
11746.1	-5.6	4.39	1068.6242	-0.0011	2/2	tigd ²²⁸⁸	LSTLTASEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(12)							
11737.1	-3.1	4.42	1068.6242	-0.0016	2/2	tigd ²²⁸⁸	LSTLTASEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(12)							
11727.1	-2.6	4.38	1068.6242	0.0004	2/2	tigd ²²⁸⁸	LSTLTASEIK ²²⁹⁷	tłpi	(12)							
5747.1	-3.0	4.30	1003.5739	-0.0009	2/3	seik ²²⁹⁸	TLPISRSPK ²³⁰⁵	vfnv	(787)							
5926.1	-2.6	4.37	1003.5739	0.0022	2/3	seik ²²⁹⁸	TLPISRSPK ²³⁰⁵	vfnv	(787)							
5753.1	-2.2	4.33	1003.5739	0.0007	2/3	seik ²²⁹⁸	TLPISRSPK ²³⁰⁵	vfnv	(787)							
24381.1	-6.9	5.11	1744.9518	0.0008	2/3	qqmk ²³²³	SRGLEEIPIF DISEK ²³³⁷	avng	(1133)							
24373.1	-6.8	4.61	1744.9518	0.0006	2/3	qqmk ²³²³	SRGLEEIPIF DISEK ²³³⁷	avng	(1133)							
24542.1	-3.7	5.48	1744.9518	-0.0007	3/3	qqmk ²³²³	SRGLEEIPIF DISEK ²³³⁷	avng	(1133)							
24531.1	-2.4	5.68	1744.9518	-0.0001	3/3	qqmk ²³²³	SRGLEEIPIF DISEK ²³³⁷	avng	(1133)							
24320.1	-2.3	5.10	1744.9518	-0.0012	3/3	qqmk ²³²³	SRGLEEIPIF DISEK ²³³⁷	avng	(1133)							
24310.1	-1.9	4.95	1744.9518	-0.0005	3/3	qqmk ²³²³	SRGLEEIPIF DISEK ²³³⁷	avng	(1133)							
28903.1	-6.5	5.34	1495.7986	-0.0006	3/3	mksr ²³²⁵	GLEEIPIFI SEK ²³³⁷	avng	(4304)							
28896.1	-5.9	5.32	1495.7986	-0.0016	3/3	mksr ²³²⁵	GLEEIPIFI SEK ²³³⁷	avng	(4304)							
28794.1	-4.0	5.06	1495.7986	0.0005	2/2	mksr ²³²⁵	GLEEIPIFI SEK ²³³⁷	avng	(4304)							
28996.1	-3.8	5.82	1495.7986	-0.0001	2/2	mksr ²³²⁵	GLEEIPIFI SEK ²³³⁷	avng	(4304)							
28803.1	-3.8	5.19	1495.7986	-0.0004	2/2	mksr ²³²⁵	GLEEIPIFI SEK ²³³⁷	avng	(4304)							
29007.1	-3.2	5.72	1495.7986	0.0001	2/2	mksr ²³²⁵	GLEEIPIFI SEK ²³³⁷	avng	(4304)							
29217.1	-2.6	4.27	1495.7986	0.0060	2/2	mksr ²³²⁵	GLEEIPIFI SEK ²³³⁷	avng	(4304)							
29207.1	-2.4	4.34	1495.7986	-0.0021	2/2	mksr ²³²⁵	GLEEIPIFI SEK ²³³⁷	avng	(4304)							
30320.1	-4.7	3.99	2243.1021	-0.0005	2/2	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA SDLIEPVTLT ²³⁶⁵	tłps	(0)							
30308.1	-4.3	3.89	2243.1021	-0.0027	2/2	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA SDLIEPVTLT ²³⁶⁵	tłps	(0)							
30330.1	-3.7	3.84	2243.1021	-0.0046	2/2	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA SDLIEPVTLT ²³⁶⁵	tłps	(0)							
30334.1	-2.2	3.98	2243.1021	-0.0046	2/2	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA SDLIEPVTLT ²³⁶⁵	tłps	(0)							
29843.1	-14.7	4.69	2775.4337	-0.0003	2/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA SDLIEPVTLT TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva	(1156)							
29828.1	-12.9	4.37	2775.4337	0.0073	2/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA SDLIEPVTLT TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva	(1156)							
30053.1	-10.3	4.85	2775.4337	-0.0009	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA SDLIEPVTLT TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva	(1156)							
29775.1	-7.3	4.29	2775.4337	-0.0071	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA SDLIEPVTLT TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva	(1156)							
30048.1	-6.2	3.89	2775.4337	0.0024	2/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA SDLIEPVTLT TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva	(1156)							
29785.1	-5.8	4.47	2775.4337	-0.0023	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA SDLIEPVTLT TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva	(1156)							

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29765.1	-5.1	4.10	2775.4337	0.0008	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEEFA SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(1156)			
30323.1	-3.6	3.87	2775.4337	0.0006	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEEFA SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(1156)			
29426.1	-3.3	3.79	2775.4337	0.0017	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEEFA SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(1156)			
30105.1	-3.1	3.50	2775.434	1.012	2/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEEFA SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(1156)			
30290.1	-2.3	3.89	2775.4337	0.0048	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEEFA SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(1156)			
30482.1	-2.0	3.79	2775.434	1.002	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEEFA SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(1156)			
30084.1	-1.7	3.66	2775.4337	0.0068	2/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEEFA SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(1156)			
29445.1	-1.3	3.85	2775.434	0.996	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEEFA SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(1156)			
28235.1	-9.0	5.47	1852.0045	-0.0001	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT LDTPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(5251)			
28031.1	-8.9	4.57	1852.0045	-0.0002	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT LDTPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(5251)			
28040.1	-8.4	4.79	1852.0045	0.0008	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT LDTPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(5251)			
28247.1	-8.4	5.24	1852.0045	-0.0011	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT LDTPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(5251)			
28081.1	-7.9	4.92	1852.0045	-0.0012	3/3	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT LDTPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(5251)			
28091.1	-7.5	5.01	1852.0045	-0.0008	3/3	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT LDTPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(5251)			
28453.1	-5.6	4.06	1852.0045	0.0020	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT LDTPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(5251)			
28438.1	-5.4	4.11	1852.0045	-0.0001	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT LDTPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(5251)			
28587.1	-3.4	3.97	1852.005	1.001	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT LDTPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(5251)			
28049.1	-1.6	4.89	1852.0045	0.0008	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT LDTPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(5251)			
28253.1	-1.5	4.34	1852.0045	-0.0011	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT LDTPLSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(5251)			
22579.1	-6.0	4.24	1431.8400	0.0017	2/2	fasd ²³⁵⁸	LIEPVTLDTP LSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(0)			
22609.1	-3.0	4.20	1431.8400	-0.0019	2/2	fasd ²³⁵⁸	LIEPVTLDTP LSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(0)			
22602.1	-2.8	4.18	1431.8400	0.0024	2/2	fasd ²³⁵⁸	LIEPVTLDTP LSK	²³⁷⁰ nlva					(0)			
39064.1	-3.0	4.20	1468.8370	0.0023	2/1	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLD	²³⁸⁴ sedl					(0)			
39072.1	-2.5	4.15	1468.8370	-0.0011	2/1	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLD	²³⁸⁴ sedl					(0)			
39869.1	-2.0	3.58	1799.9385	0.0017	2/1	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSED	²³⁸⁷ lysy					(0)			
39447.1	-7.5	3.66	3637.756	0.034	3/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK	²⁴⁰² lgtm					(610)			
39393.1	-7.0	4.44	3635.7881	0.0013	3/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK	²⁴⁰² lgtm					(610)			
39390.1	-6.3	4.50	3635.7881	0.0002	3/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK	²⁴⁰² lgtm					(610)			
39461.1	-5.9	3.68	3636.772	1.017	3/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK	²⁴⁰² lgtm					(610)			
39252.1	-5.2	3.91	3635.7881	0.0017	3/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK	²⁴⁰² lgtm					(610)			
39452.1	-5.1	3.54	3636.772	0.015	3/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK	²⁴⁰² lgtm					(610)			
39244.1	-4.9	3.77	3636.772	0.019	3/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK	²⁴⁰² lgtm					(610)			
39308.1	-4.4	3.06	3636.772	0.016	2/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK	²⁴⁰² lgtm					(610)			
39297.1	-3.3	2.94	3635.788	0.012	2/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK	²⁴⁰² lgtm					(610)			
39312.1	-3.0	3.08	3635.788	-0.013	2/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK	²⁴⁰² lgtm					(610)			
39481.1	-2.9	3.42	3636.772	0.012	3/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK	²⁴⁰² lgtm					(610)			
39247.1	-2.3	3.85	3635.7881	-0.0067	3/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK	²⁴⁰² lgtm					(610)			
10308.1	-8.3	4.93	1097.6079	-0.0004	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			
10513.1	-8.0	5.58	1097.6079	-0.0004	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			
10319.1	-7.6	5.27	1097.6079	-0.0004	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			
10524.1	-7.1	5.38	1097.6079	-0.0004	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			
14044.1	-5.0	4.78	1081.6130	0.0016	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			
14047.1	-4.1	4.81	1081.6130	-0.0016	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			
11430.1	-3.9	4.52	1098.5919	-0.0014	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			
11418.1	-3.6	4.45	1098.5919	-0.0029	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			
11131.1	-3.5	4.38	1113.6028	-0.0013	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			
11123.1	-2.8	4.36	1113.6028	-0.0017	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			
11907.1	-2.4	4.32	1098.5919	-0.0008	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			
11918.1	-2.4	4.28	1098.5919	-0.0003	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			
11116.1	-2.1	4.48	1113.6028	-0.0023	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	²⁴¹² nlqs					(1452)			

15953.1	-2.5	5.47	1701.9467	-0.0003	3/3	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGT M ANSI R NLQ S R	2417 _{wrsp}	(22)
15747.1	-1.3	4.86	1701.9467	-0.0019	3/3	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGT M ANSI R NLQ S R	2417 _{wrsp}	(22)
15755.1	-1.3	4.98	1701.9467	-0.0010	3/3	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGT M ANSI R NLQ S R	2417 _{wrsp}	(22)
19570.1	-1.2	4.88	1685.9518	0.0007	3/3	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGT M ANSI R NLQ S R	2417 _{wrsp}	(22)

1. p.N2114T#-12.99525 rs27893940 | [dbSNP](#) | [gpmdb](#) |

Protein Information

If the information below appears incomplete, press: [go](#)

ENSEMBL Protein report: ENSMUSP00000064155

Description: This transcript is not in the current gene set. Previous versions of the protein may be available on the [Protein History page](#).

Protein Sequence: —

Contributor: anonymous

store trace: yes

Column notes.

1. **spectrum**: written in the form "X.Y", where X is a unique identifier for a particular tandem mass spectrum in this data set and Y is an identifier for this particular sequence solution.
2. **log(e)**: the base-10 log of the expectation that any particular peptide assignment was made at random (*E*-value).
3. **log(l)**: the base-10 log of the sum of the fragment ion intensities in the tandem mass spectrum used to make this assignment.
4. **m+h**: the calculated mass of the protonated parent ion for this sequence assignment.
5. **delta**: the difference between the measured and calculated protonated parent ion masses.
6. **ζ**: the ratio of the measured charge of the parent ion to the number of basic sites in the assigned peptide sequence.
7. **sequence**: the sequence of the assigned peptide sequence. The sequences immediately N-terminal and C-terminal to the assigned peptide in the protein sequence are also shown.
8. **n**: the number of observations of this peptide sequence in GPMDB.
9. **ω**: the frequency of observation for this peptide in this protein (only available for some species).